

Goa

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Entry tags: City, Vedic religion, Christian Traditions, Catholic, Jewish Traditions, Islamic Traditions, Religious Place, Religious Group

Goa was the Estado da Índia capital, the bigger and main Portuguese empire city around the Indian Ocean. Known as the "Roma do Oriente", the Orient Rome, it gathered many Catholic institutions which embodied the missionary efforts of the Portuguese Crown and the Church in Asia. Religious orders, Inquisition court, many Christians temples and monasteries took place in the island of Goa, contributing to the conversion of part of the native hindu people. Under Catholic Portuguese rule from 1510 til 1961, the city became a melting pot of cultures and beliefs by the contact of many ethnic groups that lived there or had any connections with it. The following entry focus on its 16th century religious and cultural aspects.

Date Range: 1510 CE - 1600 CE

Region: Goa

Region tags: India, Konkan, Goa

Goa before Portuguese conquer belonged to the Bijapur Sultanate, serving as a trade port connected to the Arabian and Persian market. After 1510 the island of Tisvadi, where the city is located, began to be modeled as the Portuguese politics demanded. Its architecture and space shapping were elaborated to create an "Asian Lisbon", what could be also seen in its political powers. Governed by a Viceroy, containing important and powerful Portuguese institutions and made to be a Catholic fortress, Goa was an important place of the Modern Europeans affairs in Orient.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:AMH-6577-KB_Bird%27s_eye_view_of_the_city_of_Goa.jpg
- Source 2: <https://www.alamy.com/stock-photo-an-auto-da-fe-at-go-a-india-the-procession-of-clergy-and-their-victims-105287913.html>
- Source 3: <https://www.alamy.com/nederlands-gezicht-op-de-markt-van-go-a-o-leilo-que-se-faz-cada-dia-pola-menh-na-rua-direita-na-cidade-de-go-a-feito-polo-natural-por-ioan-de-linschoten-framengo-gonsi-se-quanta-foro-viden-area-pandat-plana-frequens-tectis-splendida-dives-opum-ut-mercem-hic>

properet-gemmis-auroque-nitentem-ille-abducta-procul-vendere-mancipia-congesta-huc-ideas-ganges-que-portat-et-indus-insule-et-ooo-maximae-in-oceano-p-hoogerb-monogram-fori-goensis-tabernarum-mercium-et-mercatorum-illud-frequentatnium-aperta-explicatio-per-j-h-v-linschoten-monogram-claere-opdoeninge-vande-merckt-van-go-a-met-image184889491.html

Notes: Source 1: LINSCHOTEN. Goa island, 1595. Following the legend about the map, as shown in "Itinerário, viagem ou Navegação de Jan Huyghen van Linschoten": "Representation of Goa, main mercantile city and metropolis of the kingdom, where inhabit the archbishop, the Viceroy and the Portuguese India Supreme Council . By Jan Huygen van Linschoten. Year 1595". Source 2: PICART. Auto de fé in Goa, 1723. Though this picture belongs to a period later than the one proposed in the entry, it offers an interesting view of the Catholic buildings and the Church's power over the island of Goa. The "auto de fé" was the public execution of Inquisition culprits, visibles in the image in the line after the priests. Known as the "Orient Rome", Goa was the center of Modern Catholicism in Asia, holding this title since the begginings of Portuguese occupation. LINSCHOTEN. Leilão da Rua Direita de Goa, 1595. This image shows a panorama of Goa's people in the end of 16th century. Created by the Dutch merchant, historian, artist and voyager Jan Huyghen van Linschoten, the painting represents the auctions that occurred, following the notes on it, every morning at the main street of the city, the "Rua Direita". Showing different Portugueses and Hindus groups that worked or lived in the city and its hinterland, the painting is an important source about Goa's life in the Early Modern Period.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://books.google.com.br/books?id=71htAAAAMAAJ&q=de+ceuta+a+timor&dq=de+ceuta+a+timor&hl=pt-BR&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwj32viKn8zuAhVLILkGHfkdB_oQ6AEWAHoECAEQAg
- Source 1 Description: The book "De Ceuta a Timor" (From Ceuta to Timor), wrote by the Portugueses historian Luís Filipe Ferreira Reis Thomaz, offers a wide vision about the Portuguese expansion. The chapter VII approaches the Goan society in many of its aspects, as its economy, ethnic and social aspects and its politics as the capital of Asiatic Portuguese Empire.
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/p1p2comentriosd00albu>
- Source 2 Description: Important source about Goa Portuguese conquer, the "Comentários de Afonso de Albuquerque" (Afonso de Albuquerque's commentaries) gathers letters of the captain of Portuguese forces in Asia at the beginning of its presence there.
- Source 3 URL: https://books.google.com.br/books?id=YIFIAAAAYAAJ&printsec=frontcover&hl=it&source=gbs_ge_summary_r&cad=0#v=onepage&q&f=false
- Source 3 Description: Important source about the creation of the Archbishopric of Goa in the 16th century.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:
– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1929-1930

Notes: Between the years of 1929 and 1930, traces of the old city of Chandrapura were found in Chandor, Salcete region, Goa state. There were found a brick temple complex, a damaged sculpture of a Nandi bull and other vestiges of the former Kadamba's capital. After the Portuguese conquer, the city has its name changed to Chandor, having its king slaughtered by the invaders and having its people subdued to the process of christianization.

Reference: D. Kennet , J.V. P. Rao. The Early Historic Brick Temple at Chandor (ancient Chandrapura), Goa. *South Asian Studies*, 17(1) doi: 10.1080/02666030.2001.9628594.

Reference: Nisser Dias. Ancient capital with a golden glow Read more at: http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/articleshow/55058951.cms?utm_source=contentofinterest&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=cppst.

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Chandor - Chandrapura excavation

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

– Other [specify]: Island

Notes: Following the Portuguese urban planning, Goa, after Portugal's invasion, was shaped to be a reflex of Lisbon, representing the power of the Crown in Asia. Hence, its space was modeled to bear the exterior signs and symbols of an Catholic, Mediterranean and European ruler class. Because of that, one of the main structures built following this purpose were the churches. Specially erected over hills, beyond to be seen at far distances in the landscape, they were built there due the Christian architecture tradition to place their temples over high places. It was made intentionally with the aim to approximate the church to the skies, symbolic space attached to Christian heaven beliefs.

Reference: Manuel Teixeira C.. *A forma da cidade de origem portuguesa*. São Paulo: Editora UNESP. isbn: 978-85-393-0175-1.

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

- Terracing
- Clearing
- Plantings
- Other [specify]: Dams

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: In order to focus the sacred and religious aspects of Goa, the following questions were responded in consideration of Goan Catholic structures.

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: The main structures who survived along the centuries in Old Goa are the Catholic churches, as the Se Cathedral, Bom Jesus Basilica, and Church of St. Francis of Assisi. Their shapes vary due to their architectural styles.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Many particular features concerning to the shaping of the island where Goa is located were executed not only by the Portuguese presence. Channels, dams, use of mounds to build important structures (specially churches and crosses, and, before the Catholic domination, pagodas and tulasis) were there since the older hindu occupation of the island.

Reference: Teotónio de Souza R.. Goa Medieval. A cidade e o interior no século XVII.. Lisboa: Editorial Estampa. isbn: 972-33-0943-2.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: Considering the Portuguese occupation of Goa between the 16th and 17th centuries, is possible to understand the Catholic structures built along that period as part of a bigger project of conversion of Goa people, as well as the modeling of the island space following the Portuguese urban planning.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: Demolition to get material to build another city, Panjim.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–For economic reasons

–For political reasons

–As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Other [specify]: As the city of Goa had a chronic disease problem of cholera, the government of the Estado da Índia decided to move its centrality to Panjim, also in the island of Tiswadi.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

–Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: As the following questions are referred to beliefs of the object under focus, their answers were written taking into account the Catholic beliefs and its super-human beings.

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: In general, the Portuguese cities were dedicated to the Christian God, as well as the saints taken as the city's orago.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Christian God and the Catholic saints associated with the memory of the Portuguese conquer of the city and their Asian expansion.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: The places took into account are the Goa Catholic structures and buildings.

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

Notes: Considered the Asia evangelization patron, Saint Francis Xavier is buried in Goa Good Jesus's Basilica. Because of that, the church became an important peregrination destiny to the saint's devotees.

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: Understanding that the Portuguese group (taken here as a large one with its idiosyncrasies, intern differences and hierarchies) had the Christian monuments built in Goa by Catholic initiative (by the Crown, the Church or by men of authority in general) in way to perpetuate its power in the island space. Also understanding that those monuments were related to that ethnic group (taking into account the Portuguese "ethnic" as an open, frontier and marked by moral, religious and political rules under the influence and power of the Roman Church and the Crown), it is possible to consider those monuments as a positive place of memory of that group, as well as their commemorative monuments.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

– Other [specify]: The Padroado Portuguese politic instituted an amalgama between the Crown

and the Church, assuring to the king the power to interfere in religious matters. With it, the Portugal Kingdom was able, besides other capacities, to manage and build temples. Along the Crown's efforts, religious orders were active in building new and majestic churches, counting on king's support for that.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The Portuguese expansion was believed by its rulers and priests to be under God's auspices. Thereat, was believed that the cities and fortresses conquered or builded by Portuguese formal initiative over the world were under God's protection and guidance.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– War/battle

Notes: Before 1510, the city was part of Bijapur's domains. As the Portugueses needed a site to create their main base of operations around the Indian Ocean, Goa, introduced to them by Timoja (a native hindu who was working for them), seemed to be the perfect place for that due to its geographic position, good harbor and connections to the continent. The Portuguese attack, by the way, was also motivated by the Christian rivalry against the Muslims, rivalry specially strong among Portugueses around the Indian Ocean. This conflict, wonned by the Portugueses, allowed their entrance in Concan and the establishing of Goa as the Estado da Índia's capital.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: A lot of temples, palaces and the city's structure itself received huge investiments from the Church and the Crown. In way to exalt the conversion of a former "infidel" and "gentile"

land, the size and location of temples have signified the "victory" of the Catholic occupation of Goa. Many of the Goan churches were build over demolished hindu pagodas, symbolizing the "defeat of the devil", as the hindu gods and goddesses were understood by the Catholics.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The motivations were the creation of a Portuguese capital around the Indian Ocean and the war against Muslims throughout the Portuguese Expansion in Asia.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Marbles present in the decoration of the churches probably were brought from Europe in order to make the temples resemble those in Catholic Europe.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– I don't know

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Other kinds of statues are related to the Catholic decoration of religious monuments and buildings.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Other kinds of reliefs are related to the Catholic decoration of religious monuments and buildings.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

– Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Other kinds of paintings are related to the Catholic decoration of religious monuments and buildings.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– I don't know

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Other kinds of inscriptions are related to the Catholic decoration of religious monuments and buildings.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– I don't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - Yes
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Human narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Other distinct features are related to the Catholic decoration of religious monuments and buildings.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: The churches of Ancient, Medieval and Modern Ages were temples and funerary sites, been buried under its ground notorious figures of the Catholic society at the time of the burials.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

- ↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: Considering that many churches had in its interior burials of priests, and understanding that those men were considered as sacred ones by the Catholic societies, it is possible to affirm that, even discreetly, the churches were places of a minor kind of worship of deceased people. This fact is visible by the offerings made in memory of those men (flowers specially), who, in some cases, were believed to have practiced miracles, even not yet recognized by the Roman Church.

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Yes

Notes: The worship of the saints relics is known as an important part of the Catholic cult, understanding those men and women as deified human. Even so, their cult was a minor one, though very popular, in comparison to those directed to the bigger Catholic deities.

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:
Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: There are no other kind of burials.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:
– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– Yes

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Yes

Notes: The only exception to this answer refers to the devil, related to the underground and unquestionably evil.

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: There are not other specificity.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: In Catholicism, the communication between God and his congregation could be made by all of those who worship him and in many ways. However, as the religion was strongly controlled by the Roman Church and Crown authorities, the trances, dreams, ecstasy and other allegedly forms of communication between a Catholic secular person (or even a priest in many cases) and the divine regularly became a subject of worry, inquisitorial investigation and, frequently, persecution perpetrated by the Church and by the Catholic kingdoms authorities.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: There are not other specificity.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - I don't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes

- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No

- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: There are not other specificities.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: This answer refers to the statues of Jesus, the saints and the angels.

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural monitoring approached by the questions and answers, in Catholic case, is understood to be intermediate, allegedly in the name of God, by the priests of the Roman Catholic Church.

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– No

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: There are not other specificities.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– Yes [specify]: As we are approaching the Catholic rites, the consumption of sacramental bread by the priest represents the sacrifice of Christ.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Wine and bread, though sacred when involved by the Catholic rite, are the main objects of sacrifice and offer in this religion.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: There are not other specificities.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Frequency of festivals

– specify: The festivals occurred following the Catholic religious calendar.

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Yes

Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– Yes

On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: It is hard to define the number of participants. However, the big and public festivals used to involve the whole Catholic Goan society.

Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Non-elites

Notes: The Goan Catholic castes, specially Christian brahmins and chardós, preserved the hindu commensality prohibition.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Considering as

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: The masses, one of the main Catholic rites, occurred in specific days and hours of the week (considering the European week of seven days) following the Catholic religious time. Festivals and public rites occurred following this calendar.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The Santo Oficio court, known also as Inquisition, and the Bishops courts were the main Catholic orthodoxy vigilantes of Portuguese Empire.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: In the 16th and 17th centuries, the Catholic clerks were mostly composed by European men. However, a native clerk started to appear specially from the 17th century.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Yes

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: There are not other specificities

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– I don't know

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

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